

Green Human Resource Management Practices and Corporate Performance of Access Bank Plc, Enugu

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The study evaluated green human resource management practices and corporate performance of Access Bank Plc, Enugu. The specific objectives were to; evaluate the effect of green recruitment and hiring on profitability and ascertain the effect of green training and development on customer service delivery in Access Bank Plc, Enugu. The population of the study consists of one hundred and fifty (150) staff of Access banks in Enugu state. The sample size of 109 was determined using Taro Yamane 1964. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. 83 staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. Data from the questionnaire was administered and analyzed using simple percentages, mean and standard deviation, and the research hypotheses were tested using t – test. The findings indicated that green recruitment and hiring had a significant positive effect on profitability in Access Bank Plc with (t-cal (22.536) > t-critical (2.353) and green training and development had a significant and positive effect on customer service delivery in Access Bank Plc with (t-cal (22.269) > t-critical (2.353). The study concluded that green organizations gain advantages by applying the GHRM such as: green recruitments and selection where the employees will be exposed to greening abilities; green training and development. The study recommended that among others HR managers should understand and increase the scope and depth of GHRM practices so that Access Bank Plc and other organizations can improve their corporate performance in a more sustainable manner.

ABSTRACT

Keywords: Green Human Resource Management; Corporate Performance; Green Training Development

Introduction

Businesses everywhere must adopt formal environmental strategies and programs due to the rise in global environmental concerns and the introduction of international standards on environmental issues (Daily & Huang, 2011). Businesses are slowly becoming more aware of the value of becoming green and implementing environmental management strategies. Therefore, it has been recognized that green human resource management (GHRM) is a crucial economic driver for expanding firms when the Human Resource division actively participates in the execution of green projects (Ahmad, 2015). Green human resource management basically entails putting HRM best practices and regulations into reality to encourage better resource use inside the firm. This fosters environmentalism, which further increases employee happiness and morale (Ahmad, 2015). As a result, businesses must connect their human resource policies with their green management priorities (Jabbour, 2013).

Environmentally responsible employee conduct is a key component of successfully implementing environmental policies at work, according to academics who support the significance of human resources in environmental performance (Kim, 2017). No matter the industry, business behavior that is environmentally responsible is increasingly crucial for all firms (Rayner & Morgan, 2018). The theory of HR attributions (Hewett, 2018) states that perception is crucial to consider because employees respond to HRM practices differently depending on how they perceive the reasons behind their employers' implementation. In the context of developing economies, green human resource management (GHRM) is a growing issue for the banking sector. Every nation must prioritize macroeconomic sustainability in order to increase social welfare for its citizens. As a result, environmental performance must be enhanced without hindering economic growth (Raut, 2020).

Businesses have changed to a new capacity-based system that explores green economic elements of a firm in this age of globalization, with the business world taking the lead in tackling environmental problems brought on by human harmful actions. In enterprises today, when the human resource unit is obligated to carry out the green policies, green human resource management (GHRM) is highlighted as a crucial component (Ahmad, 2015). Green human resource management practices are thus defined as the human resource management policies, plans, methods, and procedures that are put into place in businesses to improve resource utilization, lessen adverse environmental effects, and raise employee satisfaction and morale. As a result, businesses must connect their human resource policies with their green management priorities (Jabbour, 2013).

In his research on green human resource management practices and their impact on the sustainable competitive edge in the Nigerian manufacturing sector, Oyedokun (2019) noted that the components of human resource management were developed to fit the green approach, leading to the creation of green recruitment, green training and development, green compensation, and green employee relations. All businesses functioning in the environment must act as team players and collaborate with other forces in the green management concept, according to Tariq, Jan, and Ahmad's comprehensive literature analysis on the state-of-the-art in green human resource management from 2016. Once integrated within the greening idea, all human resource practices lead to substantial methods to support businesses while preserving the environment. As a result, this study examines Access Bank Plc's, Enugu, corporate performance and green people management practices.

Statement of the Problem

People are showing a strong desire to preserve this planet as a lovely place to live all throughout the world. Environmentalists, scholars, governments, and others place a strong emphasis on sustainable measures for its preservation and conservation. International conferences on topics like climate change, global warming, and carbon credits have led to the creation of particular treaties, which have symbolized the world's rigorous commitment to achieve this goal. Following these early advancements, firms want to integrate a more recent idea known as "Green Human Resource Management" into their workplace culture. For the benefit of people, society, the environment, and enterprises, green human resource management (HRM) entails policies, procedures, and systems aimed at making employees of an organization more environmentally friendly. It is important to highlight that without green human resource management techniques, staff retention and labor turnover are often poor. Additionally, brand reputation wouldn't improve in the marketplace, which would have an impact on sales. Once more, neither internally nor publicly, the organization seldom reaches its highest excellence. Additionally, risks are increased, stakeholder participation is decreased, and there are frequently significant expenses associated with a company's usage of raw

materials, water, and energy, among other things. The goal of green HRM practices is to develop, strengthen, and preserve employees' green insights so that they can perform at their highest levels in each of these roles.

Additionally, four roles—preservationist, conservationist, non-polluter, and maker—ensure that an employee will become a green employee. These give birth to an ideal condition where different human resource processes, such as hiring and firing, performance reviews, remuneration, and training, are designed in a way to produce a workforce that understands and supports environmentally friendly conduct inside the firm. Green HRM methods promote not just awareness of environmental issues but also the social and economic well-being of the company and its workers in a broader context. It may be used to cut expenses, increase efficiency, raise employee knowledge of the environment, and start green work-life balance initiatives. However, Access Bank Plc, Enugu has reportedly deemed these inadequate. In light of these contexts, Access Bank Plc, Enugu is the focus of this study's attempt to give simplified insights on certain common Green HRM practices and the impact of their application on corporate performance.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective was to evaluate green human resource management practices and corporate performance of Access Bank Plc, Enugu. The specific objectives were to;

- I. Evaluate the effect of green recruitment and hiring on profitability in Access Bank Plc, Enugu.
- II. Ascertain the effect of green training and development on customer service delivery in Access Bank Plc, Enugu.

Research Questions

The research questions are as follows;

- I. To what extent do green recruitment and hiring influence profitability in Access Bank Plc, Enugu?
- II. To what degree do green training and development influence customer service delivery in Access Bank Plc, Enugu?

Statement of Hypotheses

The hypotheses of the study are as follows;

- H₁:** Green recruitment and hiring have a significant positive influence on profitability in Access Bank Plc, Enugu.
- H₂:** Green Training and development have a significant positive influence on customer service delivery in Access Bank Plc, Enugu.

Significance of the Study

Performance is vital for the corporate organization survival. This study is important because it will find the green human resource management factors that can affect the firm performance, so that the decision makers can utilize this study and focus more on the green human resource management factors that enhances the performance of the organization.

The study is also important, as it will enrich the database literature regarding the green human resource management.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Green Human Resource Management

With time, the concept of "green human resource management" has grown in importance and importance in the business world. GHRM is a popular research topic as a result of the worldwide literature in environmental management and sustainable development expanding quickly. GHRM takes into account the economic and social well-being of the workforce and organizations in addition to environmental concerns. The GHRM is a novel idea for academics and professionals, and many of them are either unaware of it or have a vague knowledge of it. Wehrmeyer (1996) first mentioned this idea in his book.

Green HRM is the application of HRM policies to encourage resource sustainability inside businesses and, more broadly, to support environmental sustainability goals (Marhatta & Adhikari, 2013). The GHRM is a novel idea for academics and professionals, and many of them are either unaware of it or have a vague knowledge of it. management of green human resources. Activities for developing and implementing green systems inside the organization are included in green HRM. Employees are being made more environmentally conscious in order to promote sustainability, address environmental problems, and help safeguard the environment.

GHRM takes into account the economic and social well-being of the workforce and organizations in addition to environmental concerns. For the benefit of the individual, society, the environment, and the company, it refers to the policies, procedures, and processes that make workers of the corporation environmentally friendly (Opatha & Arulrajah, 2014). In order to build an organization that is socially conscious, resource-efficient, and environmentally conscious, a corporation may use a set of policies, procedures, and systems known as "green human resource management."

More importantly, green human resource management is directly accountable for developing a green workforce that comprehends, values, and adheres to green initiatives and maintains its green goals throughout the human resource management process of hiring, training, compensating, developing, and advancing the company's human capital.

Green Human Resource Management Practices

The development of a green workforce with a greater understanding of and ability to adopt a green culture inside the company is connected to green human resource management techniques. This green culture permeates all facets of HRM, including hiring, training, and learning. For an organization to create and maintain a green culture, the HRM department is crucial (Harmon, 2010). In order to fulfill organizational goals on being green, human resource functions can be leveraged to adopt green practices inside the organization. Cherian and Jacob (2012) determined that HRM techniques such employee participation, selection, remuneration, and performance management are essential for organizational success. HRM is a crucial factor in both organizational reform and strategic questions.

The fact that sustainability, environmental challenges, and HRM practices are expanding and changing quickly should be emphasized. These topics are not covered in depth in the body of works. HRM strategies including recruiting, selection, training, incentive, and pay, according to Ulrich, Cherian, and Jacob (2012), are crucial components in adopting green HRM. In order to choose green employees and provide green performance, HRM must guarantee that green processes are in place (Opatha & Arulrajah, 2014). The following are some of the key elements of green human resource management:

Green Recruitment and Hiring: Hiring people with knowledge, abilities, methods, and behaviors that align with an organization's environmental management systems is known as "green recruitment," according to Aranganathan (2018). By actively positioning the company as a top-notch green employer of choice, the business may attract individuals who are environmentally conscious (Renwick, 2008 & Jackson, 2011). The interview panel must take care to choose applicants who are environmentally conscious and who can readily fit into the organizational ideals, structures, and processes that support environmental protection. Job advertising should emphasize specific environmental ideals, such as being a socially and ecologically responsible employer, in order to recruit

environmentally conscious individuals for open positions. Additionally, organizations should state their preference for hiring individuals with the skills and dispositions necessary to take part in corporate environmental management programs.

Green Training and Development: Green training and development is the process of providing employees with working methods that assure sufficient resource utilization, decrease waste, promote energy conservation, and prevent environmental deterioration, according to Olarenrewaju and Olawayin (2021). Key components of green HRM in firms include environmental education, training, and development. A business will have a very difficult time realizing its desired environmental performance without the right education, training, and growth. The development of necessary skills and knowledge for workers through environmental training is a crucial task that helps the firm implement its corporate environmental management plans. Reduced long-distance business travel, flexible work schedules, support for telecommuting, and training to promote recycling and waste management are all excellent ways to lessen an organization's negative environmental effects (Jackson, 2011).

Green Compensation and Rewards: Green compensation and rewards are possible instruments that businesses may use as both monetary and non-monetary incentive programs in an effort to entice, retain, and inspire staff to support the organization's environmental objectives (Saeed, 2018).

Green Performance and Appraisal: According to earlier research, green performance management develops green performance indicators that include a list of green standards for all employees in performance evaluations. These standards include environmental incidents, responsibility, and carbon emission reduction, as well as how to communicate environmental concerns and policies (Delmonico. 2018.)

Green Human Resource Practices related to the study

Some of the Green Human Resource Practices related to the study include;

- I. Electronic Filing
- II. Car Sharing
- III. Job Sharing
- IV. Teleconferencing
- V. Virtual Interviews
- VI. Recycling
- VII. Online Recruitment and Training
- VIII. Energy efficient office space
- IX. Providing security to employees
- X. Selective Hiring
- XI. Self-managed and effective teams
- XII. Fair and performance-based compensation
- XIII. Green training and development
- XIV. Creating a flat and egalitarian organization
- XV. Making information easily available to those who need it.
- XVI. Employment Security

Significance of Green Human Resource Management

In the last two decades the sustainability has becoming a vital part of business strategy, by optimizing financial performance, and social and environmental issues (Boone, 2012). In order to balance between social issues and environmental risk, at the same time profitable organization are now focusing on environmental issues by adding them into their strategies. Organizational culture is very important factor in this regard and considered as a key for success of environmental policy in the organization (Bertels, Papania, & Papania, 2010). Organizational culture consists of values, assumptions, symbols and functions for conducting certain process, reflecting the thinking of employees and management regarding sustainability (Brío, Fernández, &Junquera, 2007). It is observed that HRM can change organizational culture regarding implementing certain policies and procedures for implementing environmental policies and tools (Harris & Crane, 2002). HRM creates an environment for sustainability by creating

a workforce who can understand and well aware of green culture and can contribute towards sustainability (Watson & D 'Annunzio-Green, 1996). Thus, there is a need to integrate sustainability and environmental issues into human resource management functions (Nijhawan, 2014).

Corporate Performance and its Measures

Corporate performance is a composite assessment of how well an organization executes on its most important parameters, typically financial, market and shareholder performance. Some of the measures of corporate performance include;

Profitability: Many researchers utilize traditional accounting measures of profit. One the most common indices, for example, is return on assets (Staw & Epstein, 2000& Wan & Hoskisson, 2003). Roughly, return on assets is the annual profit or net income divided by the average assets over the year. More precisely, to compute the numerator, researchers usually subtract the interest expense and the interest tax savings from the annual profit. As van Dyck, Frese, Baer, and Sonnentag (2005) highlight, return on assets is a measure of operating efficiency, reflecting the long-term financial strength of organizations. Although a ubiquitous measure, return on assets is not always an optimal measure. For example, return on assets should not be used to compare organizations in different industries. The peculiarities of any industry will bias this index. Because of the massive reserves in the insurance and banking industries, for example, return on assets will tend to underestimate the profitability of these organizations.

Return on assets differs from return on investment, which is also called the rate of return. The return on investment is usually calculated to examine the efficiency of a specific investment or initiative or to compare the efficiency of several investments of initiatives. Return on investment is merely the return of an investment that is, the gain minus the costs divided by the costs of this investment.

Productivity: Although related to profit, some researchers instead compute the productivity of employees. Roughly, productivity is the revenue divided by the total number of employees. Many researchers, however, prefer to compute the natural log of revenue divided by the total number of employees (Subramony, Krause, Norton, & Burns, 2008). Subramony, Krause, Norton, and Burns (2008), for example, showed that perceptions of pay affected productivity. That is, productivity, as measured by the natural log of revenue divided by the total number of employees, increased if employees, one year earlier, had reported they felt their pay was competitive.

Sales and Market Share: Sales is often used to gauge the performance of organizations. Nevertheless, several variants of sales have been utilized. In one study, for example, conducted by Salamon and Robinson (2008), sales relative to targets was calculated. That is, senior management had estimated the sales target of each site, depending on the product lines, characteristics of the clientele, and other factors. To compute sales performance, actual sales was divided by target sales, and then multiplied by 100. This study showed that sites in which employees felt trusted by management experienced a sense of responsibility and accountability, which translated into improvements in this sales index (Salamon& Robinson, 2008). Many related measures of sales are also used. Typical examples are total sales growth, rather than merely sales, as well as market share (Gong, Law, Chang, & Xin, 2009). Studies indicate that HR systems that relate to productivity have been shown to enhance performance, as measured by similar measures. These systems include extensive training, competitive pay that is contingent upon performance, career planning, performance appraisal, and participation in decision making (Gong, Law, Chang, & Xin, 2009).

Customer Service Delivery: Customer service delivery is the act of taking care of the customer's needs by providing and delivering professional, helpful, high-quality service and assistance before, during, and after the customer's requirements are met. Customer service is meeting the needs and desires of any customer. Some characteristics of good customer service include: Promptness, Politeness, Professionalism and personalization. In lieu of more objective measures of workplace performance, some researchers also assess subjective indices. One of the most common subjective indices is customer service.

To illustrate, in the study undertaken by Salamon and Robinson (2008), customer surveys were conducted. This particular survey comprised 10 questions, such as whether customers were assisted or greeted appropriately. Customer service was rated more favorably if employees felt trusted by management.

Subjective Estimates of Financial Performance: Some researchers utilize a measure that, in essence, combines the benefits of objectives indices with the merits of subjective indices. Specifically, participants are asked to complete a

series of subjective questions, which are intended to gauge objective indices (Rhodes, Hung, Lok, Ya-Hui Lien, & Wu, 2008). These measures have been shown to correlate appreciably with objective measures (Delaney & Huselid, 1996).

Achievement of Goals: Many indices of workplace performance disregard the goals of organizations. In one year, for example, organizations might want to invest in expensive technology, to enhance productivity in the future. The profit in this year might be negligible even if the workplace fulfills its objectives. Accordingly, profit might not be a suitable measure of performance in this context.

Therefore, to gauge workplace performance, some researchers examine the extent to which the organization has fulfilled its goals. In one study, for example, conducted by van Dyck, Frese, Baer, and Sonnentag (2005), participants rated the extent to which their "...organization achieved its most important goal in the last year" and the degree to which the organization was successful "...in comparison to other companies in the same line of industry and of (about) the same size?". As the authors predicted, organizations that manage errors effectively were more likely to fulfill their goals (van Dyck, Frese, Baer, & Sonnentag, 2005). That is, organizations were more likely to satisfy their goals, as measured by these two items, if employees communicated knowledge about errors, collaborated to resolve errors, and introduced practices that detect and manage errors expeditiously.

Measures specific to the industry: Some studies utilize measures that are specific to particular industries. In a study that examined the determinants of performance at schools, five domains were measured: academic achievement, student behavior, student satisfaction, teacher turnover, and administrative performance which was a subjective measure, as rated by principals (Ostraff, 1992).

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for this seminar was discussed below;

Green HRM Theory

We use the Ability Motivation Opportunity (AMO) theory introduced by Appelbaumet in 2000 to identify the key HRM areas that will have an impact on Environmental Management outcomes when deciding which people management issues to include in a review of GHRM. According to his theory (Appelbaumet 2000), HRM practices that improve a company's human capital through improved human capabilities lead to performance outcomes like increased productivity, decreased waste, higher quality, and increased profits. According to the AMO theory, HRM improves employees' abilities by luring and nurturing high-performing workers; increasing workers' motivation and dedication through strategies like effective performance management (PM) and contingent rewards; and giving workers the chance to participate in knowledge-sharing and problem-solving activities through employee involvement (EI) programs.

Resource-based Theory

According to resource-based theory, organizations are best positioned for long-term success when they have access to resources that are valuable, uncommon, difficult to duplicate, and non-substitutable. These strategic resources can serve as the cornerstone for the development of firm capabilities that, over time, may result in superior performance. In order to bundle, manage, and otherwise exploit resources in a way that adds value to customers and gives businesses an edge over rivals, certain capabilities are required. According to Barney (2001), these resources are collections of both tangible and intangible assets, such as a company's management abilities, organizational structures, procedures, and knowledge. According to this theory, a company can gain a competitive advantage if its human resources are developed so they have skills that its competitors cannot duplicate (Mwita, 2018). This indicated that businesses should establish an atmosphere that attracts workers who can satisfy their demands as well as one that supports their continual education in a variety of ways.

HRM has a crucial role to play in making sure that it is accomplished through Green HRM since organizational activities and operations must be in alignment with environmental conservation policies. This entails hiring environmentally conscious workers who will aid firms in developing more resourceful human capital, which serves

as a source of competitive advantage for improved organizational performance. This includes the critical role that green hiring and selection play in ensuring that businesses have staff members with the necessary green expertise.

Empirical Review

To address a specific research topic, empirical reviews look at earlier empirical studies. The empirical research under consideration are RCTs. The literature or studies that are relevant to the topic of discussion (Green Human Resource Management) practices and Corporate Performance are displayed in this empirical review section.

Green recruitment and Hiring and Profitability

Job advertising need to communicate specific environmental principles in order to draw in applicants who are environmentally conscious (e.g., be a part of the green team). By actively positioning the company as a top-tier "green employer of choice," the firm may have an easier time attracting environmentally conscious individuals (Renwick, 2008; Jackson, 2011). Businesses are starting to understand that establishing a reputation as a green employer is a good approach to draw in and hire fresh talent since it increases profitability (Phillips, 2007; Stringer, 2009). According to research by Owino and Kwasira (2016) and Mandip (2012) on the impact of green human resource management practices on environmental sustainability, hiring individuals who care about the environment would help the business achieve its goal of profitability. Really, ecologically conscious companies may draw in the talent they need to carry out corporate environmental management efforts, which ultimately helps the firm accomplish its environmental objectives.

Green Training and Development and Customer Service Delivery

Renwick et al. (2008) suggested certain green training and development practices such as training staff to produce green analysis of workspace, application of job rotation to train green managers of the future, provision of specific training on environmental management aspects of safety, energy efficiency, waste management, and recycling, development of green personal skills, and re-training of staff losing jobs in relevant polluter industries (Jackson, 2011). These skills include mitigation of wastage, and expertise in environmental protection and environmental literacy. Environmental related education, training and development are key areas of green HRM in an organization which gives rise to customer service delivery (Zakaria, 2012). Without proper education, training and development, materializing targeted environmental performance of a firm is very difficult to achieve customer service delivery. In line with this, a study by Prasad (2013) on the relationship between training and development and environmental sustainability concluded that when employees are well informed about the green procedures and policies including the vision/mission statement of the company, it enhances the sustainability-oriented benefits, company-wide initiatives like reducing greenhouse gases, creating green products.

Methodology

Research Design

The study adopted a descriptive research design. Creswell and Poth (2017) described a descriptive research design as the plan and structure for investigating the sources and type of information to be used.

Area of Study

The study on the effect of green human resource management on corporate performance using Access Bank was carried out in Enugu State with focus on the staff of the bank selected.

Sources of Data

The study utilized both the primary and the secondary sources of data.

Population of the Study

This comprises of management and staff of the selected bank in Enugu State (Access Bank). The total population studies were 150.

Determination of Sample Size

The population to be studied here is a finite one numbering one hundred and fifty (150). This permitted the use of a statistical model for determining a sample from a finite population (Yamane 1964); the model states that

$$n = N \frac{1}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

n = required sample size

N = population of the study (150)

1 = Statistical constant

e = Maximum level of error at 5%

Therefore:

$$n = \frac{150}{1 + 150(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = 150 \frac{1}{1 + (0.375)}$$

$$n = \frac{150}{1.375} = 109$$

n = 109

Method of Data Collection

The major instrument used in the data collection is the questionnaire.

Validity of Instrument

The questionnaire was given to professionals in the field of human Resource in the department for validity. The questionnaires were tested for reliability using a pilot study of 20 respondents administered to staff of Access Bank in different branch was used for the study.

Reliability of Instrument

Cronbach's reliability test was used to assess the instrument reliability. This is deemed fit because it is mostly employed by researchers as a test for research instrument reliability. The Cronbach's alpha reliability was 0.85 and the instrument was deemed reliable because it surpassed the Cronbach's Alpha benchmark given as 0.75.

Method of Data Analysis

The descriptive statistics and percentage analysis were used for the data analysis and the hypotheses were tested using t-test statistic. The statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) software version 20 was employed in the analysis of data and test of hypotheses.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Bio-Data of Respondents

The method utilized in presenting analysis in this work is the Tabular Method and percentage whereas the analysis was carried out using the parametric technic package T-test. A total of one hundred and nine (109) copies of questionnaire were distributed to the respondents and eighty-three (83) copies were retrieved displayed in Table 1.

Table 1: Questionnaire Administered to employees

<i>Number Distributed</i>	<i>Number Returned</i>	<i>Number Withheld</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
109	83	76.1%	23.9
			23.1%
			100
			100 %

Source: Questionnaire data, 2022.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	52	61.2	62.7	62.7
	Female	31	36.5	37.3	100.0
	Total	83	97.6	100.0	
Total		83	100.0		

Source: Questionnaire Data, 2022.

Table 2 shows that 61.2% of the respondents are male, while 36.5% respondents are female. This shows that the majority of respondents are males.

Decision Rule: The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics; the hypotheses were analyzed to determine the Mean score (X). A mean score of 2.4 and above was regarded as an accepted Mean to test research question. While a Mean score of 2.39 and below was regarded as rejection to test the research question.

Testing of Hypothesis

Test of Hypothesis One

How do green recruitment and hiring influence profitability in Access Bank Plc, Enugu?

The hypotheses of the study are as follows;

H₁: Green recruitment and hiring have a significant positive influence on profitability in Access Bank Plc, Enugu.

H₀: Green recruitment and hiring have no significant positive influence on profitability in Access Bank Plc, Enugu.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SA	13	15.3	15.7	15.7
	A	32	37.6	38.6	54.2
	SD	18	21.2	21.7	75.9
	DA	22	25.9	24.1	100.0
	Total	83	100.0	100.0	
Total		83	100.0		

Source: Field Survey 2022

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Access Bank computerized its recruitment and hiring exercise in order to explore the best hands.	83	2.5422	1.02768	.11280

Source: SPSS v22

As presented in table 3, the overall mean score of 2.5422 indicates that the respondents agree that Access Bank computerized its recruitment and selection exercise in order to explore the best hands.

One-Sample Test

	Test Value = 0				
	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference
					Lower
Access Bank computerized its recruitment and hiring exercise in order to explore the best hands	22.536	82	.000	2.54217	2.3178

One-Sample Test	
	Test Value = 0
	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference
	Upper
Access Bank computerized its recruitment and hiring exercise in order to explore the best hands	2.7666

Source: SPSS v22

As presented in the table 3, the calculated t-test value is 22.536. This value is greater than the critical t-test value of 2.353, i.e., $t_{cal} (22.536) > t_{critical} (2.353)$. With probability value of 0.000 which is less than P-value of 0.05, this result is significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis which state that green recruitment and hiring has a significant and positive effect on profitability in Access Bank Plc was accepted.

Testing Hypothesis Two

How do green training and development influence customer service delivery in Access Bank Plc, Enugu?

H_i: Green Training and development have a significant positive influence on customer service delivery in Access Bank Plc, Enugu.

H_o: Green Training and development have no significant positive influence on customer service delivery in Access Bank Plc, Enugu.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SA	10	11.8	12.0	12.0
	A	41	48.2	49.4	61.4
	SD	7	8.2	8.4	69.9
	DA	27	31.8	30.1	100.0
	Total	83	100.0	100.0	
Total		83	100.0		

Source: Field Survey 2022

One-Sample Statistics				
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Access Bank Plc identifies and analyses environmental training need to its staff towards developing the required skills and knowledge.	83	2.5663	1.04989	.11524

Source: SPSS v22

As presented in table 4, the overall mean score of 2.5870 indicates that Access Bank Plc identifies and analyses environmental training needs to its staff towards developing the required skills and knowledge.

One-Sample Test					
	Test Value = 0				
	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference
					Lower
Access Bank Plc identifies and analyses environmental training needs to its staff towards developing the required skills and knowledge	22.269	82	.000	2.56627	2.3370

One-Sample Test	
	Test Value = 0
	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference
	Upper
Access Bank Plc identifies and analyses environmental training needs to its staff towards developing the required skills and knowledge	2.7955

Source: SPSS v22

As presented in the table 4, the calculated t-test value is 22.269. This value is greater than the critical t-test value of 2.353, i.e., $t_{cal}(22.269) > t_{critical}(2.353)$. With probability value of 0.000 which is less than P-value of 0.05, this result is significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis which state that green training and development has a significant and positive effect on customer service in Access Bank Plc was accepted.

Discussion of Findings

Green recruitment and hiring have a significant positive effect on profitability in Access Bank Plc with $(t_{cal}(22.536) > t_{critical}(2.353))$ following the use of the descriptive and t-test analysis, the calculated t-test value is 22.536. This value is greater than the critical t-test value of 2.353. With probability value of 0.000 which is less than P-value of 0.05, this result is significant. This result is similar to the findings of Ullah (2017) which revealed that achieving sustainability in an organization is solely depended on the implementation of GHRM through efficiencies and economical utilization of Resource.

Green training and development have a significant positive effect on customer service delivery in Access Bank Plc with $(t_{cal}(22.269) > t_{critical}(2.353))$ following the use of t-test analysis and the calculated t-test value being 22.269. This value is greater than the critical t-test value of 2.353. With probability value of 0.000 which is less than P-value

of 0.05, this result is significant. This result is in line with the findings of Chowdhury, Sanju and Asaduzzaman (2017), which also confirmed that application of green HRM practices in the conduct of training and development have tendency to result into massive customer service delivery, which has led to a very strong correlation between GHRM and performance.

Summary of Findings

- I. Green recruitment and hiring had a significant and positive effect on profitability in Access Bank Plc with (t-cal (22.536) > t-critical (2.353)).
- II. Green training and development had a significant and positive effect on customer service delivery in Access Bank Plc with (t-cal (22.269) > t-critical (2.353)).

Conclusion

Access Bank Plc HR managers are aware of green human resource management procedures, according to this study report. Real Green HR practices are still in their infancy at Access Bank Plc, Enugu, according to preliminary assessment. The earliest feasible adoption of a Green HR policy and practice is advised for businesses. The system as a whole will be improved by using green training and seminars to spread knowledge of green human resource management across the organization's various levels of HR managers.

According to the study's findings, green businesses can benefit from GHRM implementation in a number of ways, including employee exposure to greening skills during recruitment and selection processes, employee training and development that focuses on teaching employees how to reduce waste and recycle and reuse materials, improve property image, draw in and keep green clients, lessen adverse environmental effects, and achieve better financial performance. It is urged to be implemented in order to achieve this.

Recommendation

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made;

- i. HR managers should understand and increase the scope and depth of GHRM practices so that Access Bank Plc and other organizations can improve their corporate performance in a more sustainable manner.
- ii. Generally, to improve green human resource management practices, the government should incorporate green HRM methods into Nigerian Labour law and promote firms that adopt green HRM.

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